

Sorption Studies of Metal Ions on modified Anion Exchange Resin, Selective Separation of Mercury(II) from other Heavy Metals

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Manuscript received 11 November 1993, accepted 19 October 1994

Aromatic complexing agents containing sulphonic acid groups have already shown analytical competence¹. Anion exchange resins incorporated with these complexing agents have been useful particularly for the separation of metal ion². These compounds display a high affinity for anion exchangers. It is therefore worthwhile to incorporate these ion-exchange materials with different types of chelating agents in order to enhance the selectivity of such materials towards metal ions and other species. The present work was therefore undertaken as an effort to develop modified exchange resins and to explore their potentiality for the selective separation of metal ions.

Results and Discussion

Amberlite resin sorbed with eriochrome black T have been found useful for the separation of important and difficult pair of metal ions. It has been found that maximum uptake of EBT is $5 \times 10^{-6} \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$. The optimum pH for the maximum sorption of EBT has been found to be 3. The sorption behaviour of metal ions on EBT form of resin as a function of pH reveals many interesting features. In case of Cu^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ca^{II} and Ba^{II} ions, the retention increases with the increase in pH. But Al^{III} , Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} show the reverse trend. Amongst various metal ions, Hg^{II} is most strongly retained by the exchanger in pH 2 medium. It is due to the fact that the ion exchange resin incorporates chelating agent EBT by π bond, which in turn reacts with metal ions to form metal chelates having different stability constants. The stronger the metal chelate formed, more strongly the metal ion will be held by the resin.

The distribution coefficient of metal ions in different concentrations of formic acid, such as 1, 2, 3, 5 M show interesting results. Distribution coefficients of metal ions, such as Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{III} , Al^{III} and Hg^{II} decrease as the concentration of formic acid increases. On the other hand, reverse trend has been observed for Mg^{II} , Zn^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Pb^{II} and Cu^{II} . It is reflected from the data on K_d values (Table 1) that Hg^{II} behaves in an exceptionally different manner as compared to other metal ions. The exceptionally high K_d value of Hg^{II} has made it possible to separate this metal ion from

TABLE 1—SOME BINARY SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON AMBERLITE RESIN IRA-400 MODIFIED WITH EBT

Sl. no.	Separation achieved	Amount(mg) loaded / (found)	Recovery %	Volume of effluent ml	Eluent
1.	Cd^{II}	11.9706 (11.9144)	99.5	40	DMW
	Hg^{II}	10.5309 (10.5309)	100.0	120	2 M HCl
2.	Pb^{II}	17.403 (17.403)	100.0	20	DMW
	Hg^{II}	10.530 (10.470)	99.4	120	2 M HCl
3.	Fe^{III}	5.584 (5.567)	99.7	20	DMW
	Hg^{II}	10.530 (10.430)	99.0	120	2 M HCl
4.	Cr^{III}	3.067 (3.041)	99.1	15	DMW
	Hg^{II}	10.510 (10.510)	99.8	120	2 M HCl
5.	Al^{III}	2.8329 (2.8329)	100.0	25	DMW
	Hg^{II}	10.530 (10.530)	100.0	120	2 M HCl

other metal ions. The utility of this material for the selective separation of Hg^{II} from other metal ions has been actually demonstrated by separating different amount of Hg^{II} from a synthetic mixture of other heavy metals.

It is apparent from the results (Table 2) that this method can be successfully employed for the removal and recovery of Hg^{II} from samples of sea water and effluent of industrial wastes.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Hg^{II} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURE OF Fe^{III} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Pb^{II} AND Cd^{II} ON AMBERLITE RESIN IRA-400 LOADED WITH EBT

Volume of DMW used for elution = 40 ml

Volume of HCl used for complete elution of Hg^{II} = 150 ml

Sl no	Amount of Hg loaded mg	Amount of Hg found mg	Recovery %
1	4.41	4.3	98.5
2	5.01	4.9	98.0
3	5.20	5.14	98.8
4	6.80	6.7	98.5
5	7.60	7.4	97.3

Experimental

Amberlite resin IRA-400 (Mesh size 20–50), sodium acetate, acetic acid, formic acid (B.D.H.) were used. Disodium salt of EDTA (S. D. Fine Chem), eriochrome black T and other reagents were of A.R. grade.

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer and an Elico LI-10T pH meter were used.

A 1% solution of EBT in absolute ethanol and 0.01 M aqueous solution of metal ions were used.

Preparation of EBT sorbed resin : To obtain modified resin the Amberlite resin IRA-400 (Cl⁻ form) was treated with 100 ppm solution of EBT for 24 h at pH 3. The resin was then washed with demineralised water until the supernatant liquid was free from excess reagent and dried at 60°.

Determination of adsorption isotherm of EBT on amberlite resin IRA-400 at pH 3 : Sorption of EBT was studied under static condition. Amberlite resin IRA-400 (0.3 g) was equilibrated for 24 h with EBT solution (20 ml) of different concentrations at constant pH 3 and at room temperature. The

equilibrium concentration of dye in the solution was then determined spectrophotometrically.

Effect of pH on the sorption of EBT on amberlite resin IRA-400 : Amberlite resin IRA-400 (0.3 g) was shaken with 100 ppm EBT solution (20 ml) for 6 h. The pH was adjusted either by adding 0.1 M HNO_3 or 0.1 M NaOH solution. The equilibrium concentration of EBT was then determined spectrophotometrically.

Metal ion retention as a function of pH : The modified resin (0.3 g) was loaded with a solution (40 ml) of the metal ion in demineralised water. The desired pH was adjusted either by adding 0.1 M HNO_3 or 0.1 M NaOH solution. The mixture was equilibrated for 24 h. The metal ion concentration was then determined by titrating it against a solution of EDTA.

Determination of distribution coefficient of metal ions : A mixture of the modified Amberlite resin beads (0.4 g) loaded with metal ion solution (40 ml) was shaken intermittently and kept for 24 h. The amount of cation before and after the equilibrium was determined by standard method³ using 0.01 M EDTA disodium salt solution as titrant. The K_d values were calculated as described earlier⁴.

Quantitative separation of metal ions : Elution technique was used for separation. A mixture of metal ion solution (2 ml) was added to a glass column (dia. 0.6 cm i.d) and allowed to pass through the column containing resin (1.5 g) with a flow rate of 8–10 drops/min. The elution of metal ions was done with appropriate eluting reagent in the usual manner keeping a constant flow rate of 18–20 drops/min. The eluted metal ion was determined titrimetrically using a standard disodium EDTA solution. Table 1 describes results of some important binary separations.

For a selective separation of Hg^{II} from a mixture of other metal ions, different amount of Hg^{II} was mixed with Fe^{III} (5.58 mg), Cr^{III} (3.06 mg), Al^{III} (2.83 mg), Cd^{II} (1.79 mg) and Pb^{II} (17.40 mg). The mixture was transferred into the column and allowed to pass slowly. The mixture of the metal ions except Hg^{II} was first eluted with 40 ml of DMW and pure Hg^{II} was then recovered by using 2 M HCl.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. A. Khan Chairman, Department of Chemistry for facilities. One of the authors (S.U.) is also thankful to MAAS for providing financial assistance.

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